

HIGH PERFORMANCE SMALL ARMS PROTECTIVE INSERT

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ABSTRACT

The Small Arms Protective Insert (SAPI) plates are an essential component for military personnel involved in armed conflict or peacekeeping missions. The SAPI plates are generally inserted into the flexible fragment or bullet protective vest carrier worn by the military personnel. Depending upon the perceived threat in the conflict area and the desirable protection level, a single vest can carry as few as one SAPI plate or as many as five SAPI plates.

A SAPI plate can consist of one or more than one type of high performance material. It can be a monolithic molded composite plate or a multi-component composite plate in combination with a hard ceramic or metal facing. The weight and coverage area of SAPI plates is critical for protection and mobility of the military personnel.

This paper examines the performance of

- a) Monolithic SAPI plates consisting of SPECTRA SHIELD® Composite Materials.
- b) Ceramic-faced SAPI plates consisting of different types of commercial ceramics backed with SPECTRA® fiber-containing, molded composite plates.

The performance of each type of SAPI plate is evaluated as a stand-alone plate without the soft vest behind the insert plate. The ballistic testing is conducted in accordance with the provisions of MIL-STD-662F using caliber 7.62 x 51mm Ball M80 and 7.62 x 54R Ball-Light-LPS. The performance of each type of SAPI plate for each threat is presented as V50, weight per unit area, and back face deformation.

1. INTRODUCTION

The current state-of-the-art flexible vests provide protection against low energy projectiles such as fragments and handgun bullets. However, these flexible vests provide practically no protection against high-energy rifle bullets traveling at two to three times the speed of a hand gun bullet. A number of rifle bullets have a steel jacket and contain a steel penetrator which can penetrate a number of traditional armor steel, armor aluminum and non-metallic breastplate materials.

However, due to technology advances made in the last ten years in the area of ballistic materials, it is possible to stop a number of such high-energy rifle bullets with a much lighter weight solution than the traditional ballistic composites and steel plates. Due to these advances in the ballistic material technologies, the breastplate inserts, also known as Small Arms Protective Inserts (SAPI) in the US, are an essential part of a vest for military and law-enforcement agencies.

Depending upon the level of body coverage, a single flexible vest may carry one and as many as five ballistic protection plate inserts. These inserts cover the front and back collars, chest, back, and the groin area of the person.

This paper reviews the high strength reinforcing viscoelastic ballistic fibers, non-woven technology to manufacture ballistic raw materials, and a method for molding these inserts. For certain SAPI plate applications, ceramics were used as a strike face material.

2. REINFORCING FIBERS

Honeywell commercialized the high strength viscoelastic SPECTRA® fibers in mid 1980's. The SPECTRA® fiber family (1,2) consists of tough man made Extended Chain Polyethylene (ECPE) (Table 1). These fibers have interesting non-linear viscoelastic properties at the high energy level associated with high-energy rifle bullets and high-speed fragments generated by hand grenades and artillery shell explosions.

Other ballistic fibers such as traditional aramids and PBO fibers have also provided interesting composites for molded breastplates and SAPI plates.

3. NON-WOVEN TECHNOLOGY

The non-woven technology for engaging bullets and fragments travelling at high speed was commercialized in late 1980's. In this process all the reinforcing fibers are lined parallel to each other, similar to a beam operation for woven fabrics, and then a binder is applied to form a continuous web of uniformly-spread, aligned fibers. The web holds the critical fiber spacing for further processing. A web of similarly aligned fibers is applied at 90-degrees to form a continuous roll. The roll product manufactured by this technique is a patented process (3), commonly referred to as "Shield" technology.

Shield technology is applicable to all types of continuous ballistic fibers such as ECPE fibers, aramid and PBO fibers.

The ballistic fibers in the non-woven technology have:

- a) no or low twist or air entanglement typical of traditional woven ballistic products;
- b) fiber distribution at micro-level which is uniformly distributed; and
- c) carefully engineered binder resins providing critical bonding between ballistic fibers for controlled delamination during projectile penetration.

4. MOLDING

The autoclave and compression molding of reinforced and unreinforced plastics is well known in the plastics and composites industry. However, for high performance ballistic materials processing, it is relatively new. Most of the ballistic composites made with fibers such as aramids and PBO will not show performance advantage as a function of molding pressure. However, SPECTRA SHIELD® product utilizes materials (non-linear viscoelastic fibers bonded together with a unique resin and controlled resin content) that show dramatic effect of molding pressure on the ballistic performance.

The high-pressure molding process

- d) enhances consolidation of fibers and resins,
- d) increases the viscoelastic modulus of molded component,
- d) increases fibers-bullet engagement and
- d) provides improved controlled delamination during projectile penetration.

5. CERAMICS

The thick, unreinforced ceramics alone may be able to stop bullets, but the resulting breastplate or SAPI plate will be fairly heavy, bulky, and extremely brittle. Relatively thin ceramics combined with fiber reinforced backing plates are used in certain types of breastplates and SAPI plates to strip the steel jacket of the bullet, blunting the steel penetrator and in some cases disintegrating the entire bullet. The ballistic resistance of a ceramic depends upon the type of ceramic, thickness of the ceramic, and process of integration with the right amount of backing materials.

In recent years, the ceramics have also undergone a technology evolution. This includes thin lightweight ceramics based on aluminum oxide, or silicon carbide or boron carbide materials.

The SAPI plates with ceramic facing are used only for chest and back area and cover practically half the body area (compared to four to five breastplates per kit used in many European countries.)

6. BALLISTIC THREATS

The common ammunition that the breastplate and SAPI plates are designed to stop includes:

M80 ball (7.62X51), NATO ball (7.62 X51), AK-47 Kalashnikov (7.62 X 39), M193 (5.56X 45), SS109 RG (5.56X45), SS109FN (5.56 X45), M855 (5.56 X 45), WIN, 7.62 X54 LPS, 7.62 X 54 L (Dragnov).

The velocities of high-energy rifle bullets are two to three times higher than the velocity of handgun bullets. Although the weights of some of the rifle bullets are lower than handgun bullets, the energy associated with rifle bullets is several fold higher than that of a handgun bullet. This is due to the momentum of the bullets. The momentum is calculated as a function of the square of the bullet's velocity. Therefore, if there are two identical bullets with an equal mass but one bullet is traveling twice the velocity of the other bullet, then the bullet with twice the velocity will have four times more energy associated with it.

7. MATERIALS

For high performance breastplates and SAPI plates, ballistic materials used are:

SPECTRA SHIELD® ballistic material
Fabric prepregs made from SPECTRA® fiber
GOLD FLEX® ballistic material
Ceramic-Faced SPECTRA SHIELD® ballistic material
Ceramic-Faced GOLD FLEX® ballistic material

Selection of proper ballistic material for the breastplate and SAPI plates is dependent on a number of factors. The first and foremost factor is the ballistic threats. The entire range of specified bullets should stop in the plate with deformation within the specified limit. The other factors include method of manufacturing, the weight limitation, the multiple hit capability, durability and cost of labor to assemble the breastplate

7.1 SPECTRA[®] Fiber-Containing Composites

The SPECTRA[®] fiber-containing composites offer a number of choices for breastplates. These ballistic materials (Table 1) include:

SPECTRA SHIELD[®] PCR
SPECTRA SHIELD[®] PLUS PCR
SPECTRA SHIELD[®] PLUS VE
Fabric prepreg made with SPECTRA[®] fibers.

Except for the SPECTRA SHIELD[®] PLUS VE and the fabric composites made with SPECTRA[®] fibers and a rigid thermoset matrix, these commercial “Shields” contain a semi-rigid thermoplastic binder. The thermoset binders provide a relatively high temperature performance with low backface deformation.

The SPECTRA SHIELD[®] materials offer a lightweight breastplate for the NIJ Level III and the NATO ball bullets. In a number of countries, such as France, Spain, Turkey and India, the breastplate molded with any of these materials offers one of the lightest weight breastplate solutions suitable for multiple hits (Table 2).

7.2. GOLD FLEX[®] Ballistic Material

GOLD FLEX[®] ballistic material is a second generation non-woven “Shield,” based on aramid fibers. The GOLD FLEX[®] product offers a number of advantages over woven aramid fabric prepreg. This includes thinner molded backing material with higher mechanical stiffness. Limited amount of testing shows that GOLD FLEX[®] ballistic material can be molded and used as backing for ceramic-faced SAPI type plates (Table 4).

7.3 Fabric Prepreg Made from SPECTRA[®] Fibers

The SPECTRA[®] fabric (Style 903) prepreg with a thermoplastic or thermoset resin can be molded as backing for ceramic-faced breastplates and SAPI plates. The system offers an economical solution as an alternative to SPECTRA SHIELD[®] materials system. However, there is a potential weight penalty in the range of 10 to 15%.

7.4 CERAMIC-FACED BREASTPLATE

Traditionally, the ceramic-faced breastplates and SAPI plates consist of molded composites that are faced with ceramic. When impacted with a high-energy bullet, the ceramic facing disintegrates. As the ceramic facing breaks into smaller pieces energy associated with the bullet is absorbed. Then the composite backing absorbs the fragmented metals from the bullet and the shattered ceramics. Such ceramic-faced composites are used with the flexible vest to defeat high-energy rifle bullets.

7.5 MONOLITHIC BREASTPLATE

The monolithic breastplates and SAPI plates molded with 100% SPECTRA SHIELD® composite material and high-pressure molding technology defeat NIJ Level III and other similar-energy rifle bullets, such as AK-47 and Dragnov, without the ceramic facing. This is one of the major advantages of using SPECTRA SHIELD® composite material. The breastplates without ceramic are lighter by as much as 30% compared to ceramic-faced breastplates for NIJ Level III.

7.3 TYPES OF CERAMICS

Three common types of ceramics are:

Aluminum oxide
Silicon carbide
Boron carbide.

The ceramics are generally available in a number of thicknesses and sizes. The size of the tiles varies from a few millimeters to monolithic ceramics covering the entire breastplate. The breastplate and SAPI plate ceramics are available in flat, single curvature, and double curvature configurations.

Aluminum oxides are the most common types of ceramic for breastplates because of their low cost and adequate performance. The silicon carbide tiles are the second best in terms of cost with improved performance, and boron carbide are the lightest, highest-performing tiles, but also the most expensive.

A comparison of ballistic performance for all three types of tiles with SPECTRA SHIELD® PCR hard composites is shown in Table 3.

8. MOLDING

8.1 AUTOCLAVE

The autoclave fabrication process for composite materials is fairly common for aerospace and structural composites where resin contents are fairly high (40-65% by weight), viscosity of B-stage prepregs are below 1000 poise and resin flow starts at a fairly low pressure. The void content of these composites is typically less than 1% when processed under standard vacuum and pressure conditions. However, the majority of ballistic materials starve in resin content (typical 5 to 20% by weight) and consist of fairly high viscosity resins (approaching millions of centipoises) at standard autoclave processing conditions. The ballistic composites processed in an autoclave can have potentially

- a) uneven surface on one side;
- b) practically no resin flow in majority of materials;
- c) void contents touching 10-20%;
- d) higher back face deformation; and/or
- e) lower ballistic performance for stand-alone breast plate inserts.

8.2. MATCH-DIE MOLDING

Match-die molding or high-pressure molding utilizes a shaped (flat or curved) mold and a high-pressure hydraulic press with heating and cooling system. The ballistic material is stacked in a desired configuration in the mold which is kept at the processing temperature. Molding pressure is applied either in a single stage or in stages. After a relatively short duration compared to autoclaves, a cooling cycle is started. Once material has reached the desired temperature, the mold is opened and molded product is released from the mold.

The match-die, high pressure molding of non-linear viscoelastic materials typically exhibits

- a) fairly uniform and glossy surfaces;
- b) thickness uniformity;
- c) higher structural stiffness;
- d) low back face deformation; and
- e) higher ballistic performance when tested as stand-alone plate.

9. TESTING

Testing of breastplates and SAPI plates is divided into three parts. In the first part, the flexible vest is tested against the specified fragment or bullet threat. In the second part, the hard-armor molded panel is tested with the clay backing. In the final test, both the flexible vests and the hard-armor plate are combined and tested on clay against the high-energy rifle bullet. While military vest certification varies depending on its use, in general the design requirements for the vest is that bullets should stop in the hard armor plate and not in the flexible fragment armor vest.

Each country has a slightly modified specification for testing. The two common standards for testing the flexible vest and breastplates are the NIJ Standard (8) and the MIL-STR-662F (5).

10. CONCLUSION

The monolithic SPECTRA SHIELD[®] ballistic material molded plates offer one of the lightest breastplate designs without a heavy ceramic facing for the NIJ level threat III and other threats including the AK-47, the NATO ball and the Dragov bullets.

The ceramic-faced SPECTRA SHIELD[®] ballistic material plates provide one of the lightest SAPI plates to defeat high-speed rifle bullets with steel penetrator.

The SPECTRA[®] fiber-containing fabric composites and the SPECTRA SHIELD[®] ballistic material offer lightweight choices for breastplates and SAPI plates.

11. REFERENCES

1. A.Bhatnagar, D.Lang, "High Performance Armor Materials", Solider Modernization Seminar, Ottawa, (1996)
2. L.Lin, A.Bhatnagar, H.W.Chang, "Ballistic Energy Absorption of Composites-III", SAMPE Technical Symposium, (1992)
3. For example, US 4,916,000

4. Military Specification Projectiles, Caliber's .22,.30,.50 and 20 mm Fragment Simulating Projectiles, MIL-P-46593A (ORD)
5. Military Standard "Ballistic Test for Armor" MIL-STD-662F (1987)
6. French SCERCAT No 37-07 "Gilet pare-balles serie 3", Feuillet No 17, September 1995
7. A.Bhatnagar, "New Technologies and Materials for Military Helmets and Body Armor" PASS 173-183 (1998).
8. T.Kuroki, Y Nomura and K Yabuki, "Study of Ballistic Performance of Zylon (PBO) fabric" PASS 191-195 (1998)
9. National Institute of Justice "Ballistic Resistance of Police Body Armor" NIJ Standard 0101.04, Sep (2000).

TABLE 1

SPECTRA® FIBER-CONTAINING COMPOSITES FOR BREASTPLATES AND SAPI-TYPE PLATES

MATERIAL	THICKNESS (mm)	WEIGHT (g/sq.m)
<i>SPECTRA SHIELD</i> ® PCR (*)	0.15	132
<i>SPECTRA SHIELD</i> ® PLUS PCR (*)	0.10	95
<i>SPECTRA SHIELD</i> ® VE(**)	0.30	285
<i>SPECTRA</i> ® fiber-containing fabric VE (**)	0.50	296
(*) Thermoplastic matrix	(**) Thermoset matrix	

TABLE 2

BREASTPLATE FOR NIJ LEVEL III & NATO BALL

MATERIAL	WEIGHT (Kg/sq.m)
<i>SPECTRA SHIELD</i> ® PCR	17.5
<i>SPECTRA SHIELD</i> ® PLUS PCR	14.5
<i>SPECTRA</i> ® fiber-containing fabric VE NOT RECOMMENDED	

TABLE 3

HARD ARMOR, 30 CAL. AP BULLET
V50 = 823 mps
BACKING *SPECTRA SHIELD*® PCR

MATERIAL	AREA DENSITY (Kg/sq. m)
ALUMINUM OXIDE	39.0 – 43.9
SILICON CARBIDE	31.7 – 36.6
BORON CARBIDE	26.8 – 31.7

TABLE 4

SAPI-TYPE PLATE

SOVIET 7.62 X 54 R, LPS

CERAMIC A= SILICON CARBIDE ,4" X 4"X0.230"

CERAMIC B= ALUMINUM OXIDE , 4" X 4"X 0.350"

CERAMIC	MATERIAL	AREAL WEIGHT (Kg/sq. m)	DEFORMATION (mm)
A	<i>SPECTRA SHIELD</i> ® PCR material	5.27	42
B	<i>SPECTRA SHIELD</i> ® PCR material	8.56	50
A	<i>GOLD FLEX</i> ® material	5.28	49
B	<i>GOLD FLEX</i> ® material;	8.57	52